

Soil and Crop Management

Effect of pretransplanting submergence and green manure on yield and sodic soil improvement

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A field experiment in split-plot design evaluated the effect of 0, 1, and 2 wk field submergence before transplanting with and without green manure on yield and sodic soil improvement. The experiment was replicated three times.

Response of rice to pretransplanting submergence with and without *Sesbania* green manure. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

The highly sodic soil of the test plots had pH 10.25, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) of 86, 0.48 meq of exchangeable Ca + Mg/100 g soil, 0.21% organic C, 2.85% CaCO₃, 10.8 meq CEC/100 g soil, and 20 t gypsum requirement/ha.

Gypsum was applied at 10 t/ha in all 40-m² plots and water was ponded for 1 wk before sowing *Sesbania aculeata* (10 May 1985). The green manure crop was irrigated as required. Plots without a green manure crop were irrigated at the same time.

Sesbania was incorporated at 50 d and plots were submerged 0, 1, and 2 wk before transplanting Jaya rice in standing water (12 Jul). Plots were kept submerged throughout rice crop growth. Urea at 150 kg N/ha and

ZnSO₄ at 40 kg/ha were applied to all treatments. Half the N and all the Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk. The crop was harvested 30 Oct.

Green manuring significantly enhanced yield (see figure), contributing 111.6 kg N/ha. One week of submergence with incorporated green manure significantly improved yield over no flooding and equaled 2 wk submergence. Yield with pretransplanting submergence without green manure was significant only with 2 wk submergence. Continuous submergence improved the sodic soil and green manuring further decreased pH and exchangeable sodium (see table). *S*

Effect of presubmergence and green manure on N contribution to rice crop, soil pH, and ESP at 0-15 cm soil depth.^a CSSRI, Karnal, India.

N source	Treatment Presubmergence (wk)	Biomass (t/ha)	N turned in (kg/ha)	At transplanting		After harvest	
				Soil pH	ESP	Soil pH	ESP
No green manure, 150 kg N/ha	0	—	—	9.6	45	9.4	36
	1	—	—	9.6	42	9.3	34
	2	—	—	9.5	42	9.3	34
Green manure, 150 kg N/ha	0	3.8	111.5	9.3	35	9.0	30
	1	3.8	110.8	9.2	32	8.9	28
	2	3.9	112.6	9.1	32	8.8	25
LSD (0.05)	Biomass and N	NS	NS	—	—	—	—
	Green manure	—	—	0.22	3.2	0.20	2.4
	Submergence	—	—	0.12	1.5	0.11	1.2

^aInitial soil pH 10.25, ESP 86. Gypsum was applied at 10 t/ha before sowing *S. aculeata*.

Response of rice to different N fertilizers

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The relative efficiency of slow-release N fertilizers was studied in 1984 rabi (Oct-Feb) and 1985 kharif (Jun-Sep). Test varieties were IR20 (135 d) in rabi and TKM9 (110 d) in kharif.

The experimental field was sandy loam, with pH 4.9 and 288 kg N, 33 kg P, and 112 kg K/ha available nutrients. In the split-plot design, replicated three times, four N sources were applied at two levels in the main plot and two application methods were compared in subplots. P and K were applied to all plots at transplanting. Urea supergranule (USG) was placed in alternate rows as basal and topdressed; prilled urea (PU), neem cake-blended

urea, and coal tar-coated urea were incorporated just before transplanting (basal) and broadcast at the time of topdressing.

Application methods were 100% N applied as basal and incorporated just before transplanting and 50% N applied as basal and 50% N as topdressing in 2 equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation.

During kharif, the interaction of N level and sources significantly